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Towards perfect MWIR transparency using oblique angle deposition

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Abstract: This work reports the development of a perfect antireflective coating designed to operate over the 3.7-4.8 μm MWIR region, in order to improve the optics used in thermal detection systems. A simulated stack with 99.97% average transmittance is designed for a silicon support using an effective refractive index approach. This structure made of two layers is deposited by electron beam evaporation to achieve an optical transmittance as high as 99.21% and a 98.56% average. These performances are similar to that reported for the best MWIR interferential antireflective systems, but rely on a much simpler design. The first layer is fabricated by oblique angle deposition to obtain Ge nanocolumns that are then coated with a dense MgF_2 capping film. Because environmental pollution can cause light absorption in the infrared region, different techniques are combined to provide key insights about the nanostructure and the related optical properties: ellipsometry, spectrophotometry and scanning-transmission electron microscopy combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry. With this approach, essential chemical aspects like oxidation, water adsorption in the Ge layer and intermixing at the Ge/ MgF_2 interface are evidenced. Advanced models based on effective medium approximation, considering this set of information, are addressed here to gain a better description of the optical response of the surface. In a context of performance optimization of this almost perfect antireflective bilayer, new routes and perspectives to limit or reduce these compositional issues are proposed.

1. Introduction

Infrared (IR) optics are used in a large variety of domains such as astronomy,[1] building diagnostics [2] or agronomy.[3] In the IR region, the mid-wavelength-IR (MWIR) band covering the wavelengths from 3 μm to 5 μm plays a key role. This range forms one of the most important atmospheric transmission window [4] and it is particularly suitable for thermal imaging technologies in both civil and military applications related to navigation, targeting,

surveillance and safety under all environmental conditions including fog, arctic, tropical, desert, sandstorm and maritime [5,6]. Unfortunately, materials currently used in the actual devices suffer from important reflection losses due to their high refractive index, which degrade significantly their performances. For example, at normal incidence, silicon with a refractive index of 3.4 will reflect about 30% of the light coming from the air at its interface. To limit light reflection, an antireflective (AR) coating can be deposited on top of the surface of interest.[7,8] Such treatment generally relies on destructive interferences created by the multiple reflections occurring when light encounters a material with a different refractive index. Up to date, the best AR coatings reported in the literature for Si and Ge optics in the MWIR region presents an average transmission of 98.5% over 3.6-4.9 μm . [9] For IR systems containing many optical elements and devoted to operate in a low light environment, further enhancement of the transmission at each interface even by only a few percent is essential. For example, a 1.5% increase of transmittance of a single interface, from 98.5% to 99.97%, can lead to 21% of overall transmittance gain for an optical system composed of 8 lenses (16 interfaces). However, the complexity of the interferential MWIR AR systems (multilayer stacks of different materials) and the small number of refractive indices available for transparent materials in the IR are currently limiting the design possibilities for improved MWIR optics.

To tackle this problem, a bottom-up process like oblique angle deposition (OAD) of thin films can be considered as an alternative since it has recently attracted much attention in the field of optics. By taking advantage of the self-shadowing effect, this method can be used to control the porosity rate at the nanoscale and thus to control the effective refractive index of the deposited material.[7] The preparation of novel materials with tunable optical indices is suitable not only for the design of simpler and more efficient AR systems, but also for other coatings like distributed Bragg reflectors.[10] This OAD approach has been used many times

to prepare AR surfaces covering the visible and/or near-IR ranges, mostly for photovoltaic applications, using SiO₂, TiO₂, ITO and Ge materials [11–13]. However, to our knowledge, there are no scientific reports that have already focused on OAD deposition for the engineering of AR coatings in the deeper IR region such as the MWIR band.

The paper reports for the first time the design and fabrication of a simple and highly efficient antireflective coating in the MWIR region (3.7-4.8 μm) using the oblique angle deposition process: a bilayer system composed of a germanium OAD film capped by a dense MgF₂ layer.

From advanced characterization, by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), IR spectrophotometry, ellipsometry and optical simulations, important nanostructural and chemical aspects influencing the AR MWIR properties are exposed. Combining these results generally overlooked in the literature, an advanced description for the optimization of the optical performances is presented.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Sample preparation

The experimental setup used for the deposition consists in a vacuum chamber (base pressure 2.10⁻⁶ mbar) equipped with an electron-beam evaporator. Germanium OAD layers were deposited under a pressure of 2.10⁻⁶ mbar with various angles of incidence from 0° to 82° by e-beam evaporation method using a germanium charge (Photonic sense[®] purity>99.999%) on 2 mm thick (001) silicon substrates. The molten spot in the crucible has a diameter of 5 cm and the distance between the crucible and the sample is 70 cm leading to an angle deposition divergence of Δα=4°. Moreover, an estimated error of 10% of the deposition angle is assumed. To make easier further cross-sectional TEM observations of these samples, the substrates were intentionally placed with one <110> crystallographic axis perpendicular to the incoming

deposition flux. A quartz crystal monitor was used to control the thickness and assure the deposition rate of 10 \AA/s in normal incidence. Temperature of the deposition chamber was monitored and found to rise from 21°C at the beginning of the evaporation to a value of 60°C at the end of the process.

This elaboration set-up is not equipped with an in-situ adjustable orientation sample-holder, so the bilayer was made in two steps. For the first step, a germanium OAD layer was deposited at an angle of 65° with the condition of elaboration previously described. For the second step, the chamber was opened to modify the angle of incidence to a value of 0° . MgF_2 was then evaporated from pellets (Umicore[®] 99.99% purity) and deposited onto the germanium OAD layer. The deposition chamber was heated at a temperature of 200°C to anneal the sample and MgF_2 layer was then grown at the same temperature and a deposition rate of 10 \AA/s under a pressure of 2.10^{-6} mbar. This whole process was repeated a second time to coat the silicon substrate on both sides.

2.2. Optical characterization

To access to optical properties of monolayer and bilayer, spectrophotometry and ellipsometry measurements were carried out for each sample. Transmittance and reflectance spectra were recorded with a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer. A great attention was dealt to assure a good parallelism for the silicon substrates as a non-parallel substrate can cause measurements to vary with the orientation of the sample. Transmittance and reflectance acquisitions were repeated 4 times for each sample giving a repeatability of 0.1%. The in-situ annealing transmittance measurement was made with a Woollam IR-Vase ellipsometer. Ellipsometry experiments were performed on the same Woollam IR-Vase ellipsometer.

2.3. Morphological and nanostructural characterizations

The overall morphology and thickness of the films were studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a FEG 7001F-TTLS JEOL microscope at an accelerating voltage of 30 kV.

To get additional insights about their nanostructure, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) experiments were conducted in a FEI Talos F200S microscope operated at 200 kV and equipped with a Super-X energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDX) system that includes two silicon drift detectors. Local compositional analyses were performed by combining high-angle annular dark field imaging (HAADF) and EDX acquisitions using the scanning (STEM) mode. EDX elemental maps of 100x100 pixels were obtained using a dwell time of 100 ms, energy resolution of 5 eV/channel over 4000 channels, and spatial drift correction. Cross-sectional specimens were thinned down by mechanical polishing using a tripod apparatus up to less than 10 μm followed by argon ion milling in a GATAN PIPS system (3.5 keV, $\pm 7^\circ$ incidence). To minimize irradiation damage, the final step was performed at 2.5 keV, $\pm 5^\circ$ during 5 min up to electron transparency.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. AR design for silicon substrate in the 3.7 to 4.8 μm range

AR coatings are usually designed with predefined materials, i.e. prefixed refractive indices. The thicknesses and number of layers are then optimized with a numerical iterative process to minimize the reflection at the interface, for a defined range of wavelength, by maximizing destructive interferences[14]. Herein we expected that the OAD technique could allow obtaining any effective refractive index values below that of the dense material counterpart. From this hypothesis, the optimization method used here for an AR coating can theoretically be used to improve the performance of any kind of optical thin film coating, for any substrate

and any range of wavelength. In this paper, we have thus optimized a simple bilayer AR coating design for a silicon substrate (both sides treated) in the 3.7-4.8 μm region. Silicon was chosen because it is transparent in this infrared range, inexpensive, with well-known optical properties, and widely used in the industry. The AR optimizations were made with the commercial SCOUT software using the downhill simplex method with four free parameters for the bilayer coating (layer thickness and refractive index of each layer).[15] **Figure 1** presents the transmittance spectrum of this optimized AR bilayer (with fictitious refractive index) compared with a conventional interferential system using dense materials: YbF_3/ZnS . This stack was designed with the Macleod software.[14] The optimal refractive indices of the optimized AR bilayer and those of the simulated classical interferential stack have been added on Figure 1.

The simulated transmittance of the multilayer interferential stack is closed to the commercial specifications: 99.02% of average transmittance for the 3.7-4.8 μm range.[16,17] According to these simulations, it appears clearly that the transmittance of a silicon wafer can be increased significantly by reducing and controlling precisely the effective refractive index of the surface. In the present case, an average value of 99.97% over 3.7-4.8 μm may be reached with two layers having refractive index target values of 2.52 and 1.37 and thicknesses target of 427 nm and 779 nm respectively. This represents a 0.95% increase relative to the conventional interferential treatment. Among materials able to lead to these refractive indices, germanium was chosen because the latest is a well-known transparent material in the infrared region and because its high refractive index ($n=4$ at $\lambda=4 \mu\text{m}$) potentially permits to cover a wide range of effective refractive index using OAD geometries.[18]

3.2. Ge OAD films: microstructural aspects and consequences on their refractive index as a function of deposition angles.

To reach a refractive index close to the design value ($n=2.52$ at $\lambda=4 \mu\text{m}$), a calibration step of the effective refractive index obtained for Ge OAD is necessary. This was achieved by varying the deposition angle of Ge from $\alpha=0^\circ$ to a value of $\alpha=82^\circ$. **Figure 2.a** shows a SEM cross-section and **Figure 2.b** is a plane view micrograph of a Ge OAD thin film taking, as an example, the thin film deposited with a deposition angle $\alpha=65^\circ$. Pores and empty spaces are clearly seen on the top surface, which indicate the porosity of the films and the isolated nature of nanocolumns. The cross-section shows well separated inclined nanocolumns. This tilted angle β of the nanocolumns with respect to the Si surface depends on the deposition angle α : a value $\beta=62^\circ$ was found in the present case for $\alpha=65^\circ$. This tilt angle is higher than the one reported by Gruner *et al.* [19] These differences may be ascribed to our large different setup chamber parameters as a higher divergence of the vapor flux, higher pressure in the chamber, effect of the temperature rise which can increase significantly the surface diffusion and to measurement errors of the deposition angle. However the objective being to calibrate the optical properties of a series of Ge, those uncertainties can be considered as acceptable. The porosity of OAD films increases with the deposition angle α due to an increasing shadowing effect and a lower ad-atom mobility on the film surface.[20]

The effective refractive index of the Ge OAD thin films has been extracted from infrared ellipsometric and spectrophotometric measurements. For that purpose, we first determined the dispersion law (Cauchy law) of the Ge thin film deposited at a normal incidence ($\alpha=0^\circ$), considered as a dense and homogenous Ge thin film on silicon substrate. Then, taking into account the heterogeneous behavior of the nanostructured OAD thin films,[21] a mixing law has been used (Bruggeman effective medium approximation BEMA) for each deposition angle. It is assumed here that the nanocolumns have the same optical behavior as the

germanium dense material (obtained at $\alpha=0^\circ$) so the mixing law is the result of a mixture of this bulk material and voids. The refractive index drop observed at higher deposition angle was simulated from BEMA model by taking into account the insertion of a volume fraction of air in the Ge layer, which is assumed to correspond to the film porosity.

In the 2-6 μm spectral range, **Figure 3** shows a good fit of ellipsometric and spectrophotometric measurements on a Ge OAD thin film elaborated at $\alpha=65^\circ$ except for local discrepancies (located for example close to 3 μm and 10 μm), coming from pollution (discussed later). The simple BEMA optical model used for this simulation leads to 42.8% of porosity and an effective refractive index of $n=2.39$ at $\lambda=4 \mu\text{m}$. This model correctly fits the ellipsometric measurements for all deposition conditions. **Figure 4** presents the evolution of the porosity and effective refractive index of Ge OAD thin films at $\lambda=4 \mu\text{m}$ as function of the deposition angle. It shows that the effective refractive index of this material can be controlled from a value of 3.97 for $\alpha=0^\circ$ to a value of 1.75 for $\alpha=82^\circ$. This also confirms that Ge is promising candidate to design AR films because it allows to cover a wide range of effective refractive indices using the OAD technique, as demonstrated by other authors.[18]

3.3. Nanostructure and chemical analyses of the bilayer

In consideration of the preliminary results, the best experimental bilayer should be made using a germanium OAD bottom layer obtained with $\alpha=60^\circ$ or with $\alpha=65^\circ$ because these angles lead to the closest refractive index respectively ($n=2.58$ and $n=2.40$) compared with the designed target ($n=2.52$). It must be added that the design was made with effective refractive indexes independent of the wavelength. By considering the dispersion law of the real refractive indexes, deposition of Ge OAD layer with $\alpha=65^\circ$ was preferred since it provides slightly enhanced AR performance. This ideal index of the top layer ($n=1.37$) can be reached with this type of Ge nanostructuring (using an incident close to $\alpha=88^\circ$, not presented here).

Instead, a dense MgF_2 film deposited in normal incidence has been chosen as capping layer because its refractive index matches the ideal one ($n=1.37$). In addition, this encapsulating layer can help ensuring the mechanical and chemical stability of the sample by minimizing the adsorption or absorption of environmental pollutants.

At this stage, chemical aspects of this study are considered because, as shown in Figure 3, they can impact the optical performance of our stacks (refer for example to the singularities located at about $3\ \mu\text{m}$ and $10\ \mu\text{m}$). This discussion is based on two experiments: the transmittance of the nanostructured Ge thin film ($\alpha=65^\circ$) on the IR spectral range of $2\text{-}13\ \mu\text{m}$ (**Figure 5**) and an elemental analysis of the complete bilayer (including the nanostructured Ge thin film and the dense MgF_2 cap) from scanning TEM (STEM) energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry (**Figure 7**).

Various chemical features coming from pollutants can be observed on Figure 5. The good match between the experimental spectrum and the simulation (described later in detail) attests that all of them have been identified. Those due to silicon contamination (referenced in black) are out of the range of interest $3.7\text{-}4.8\ \mu\text{m}$. Additional components coming from the nanostructured Ge thin film (referenced in blue and green) have been observed: two of them are attributed to water (located at $2.9\ \mu\text{m}$ and $6\ \mu\text{m}$), the other one to germanium dioxide (located at $11.8\ \mu\text{m}$). According to PubChem,[22] another absorption peak of GeO_2 should be present around $3.7\ \mu\text{m}$ but its intensity is probably too small to identify it precisely. As demonstrated by other authors,[23–25] these results show that, being a porous medium, the nanostructured Ge thin film is subjected to oxidation as well as water adsorption. These two elements were thus added in the BEMA mixing model and a regression was made on transmission (Figure 5) and ellipsometry (**Figure 6.a**) spectra to determine the volume ratio of the different components. Thus, the germanium OAD layer deposited at $\alpha=65^\circ$ was found to

be composed of 44.4% of Ge, 14.9% of GeO₂, 17.2% H₂O and 23.5% of air as illustrated on Figure 5.

Finally, the resulting effective refractive index of this composite thin film is given in Figure 6.b. From the obtained extinction coefficient, we demonstrate that H₂O and GeO₂ will generate non-negligible absorption in the 3.7-4.8 μm range.

To gain further insights into the bilayer nanostructure and to confirm the chemical information extracted from optical spectroscopies, local analyses have been performed by TEM (Figure 7). An overview of this system observed along a <110> direction of the Si substrate is shown in bright field in Figure 7.a. This observation confirms the morphology of the porous Ge OAD layer made of tilted nanocolumns, and the dense character of the MgF₂ film. The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns recorded in the different regions also indicate that the Ge nanocolumns are amorphous whereas the MgF₂ layer has a polycrystalline rutile structure, which is commonly observed after deposition by PVD processes.[26] Note that these TEM measurements were performed prior to the optimization of the thickness layers, which was done to match the designed performances. This explains why the layer thicknesses in Figure 7 differ from the other results from SEM and ellipsometry, which were obtained on already optimized systems. However, the main purpose of TEM in this work was focused on the chemical characterization of the system which is expected to be unchanged after optimization.

The STEM-EDX analysis provides relevant compositional information of the bilayer. According to the elemental maps (Figure 7.b), a clear chemical evidence of Mg and F insertion inside the porosity of the bottom Ge layer is pointed out (see arrows), which contributes to form an intermixing layer at the interface between the Ge OAD and MgF₂ films. The extension of this interface layer is about 50 nm. The presence of oxygen is also visible in the Ge nanostructured film in agreement with the IR optical analysis predictions (Figure 5).

Quantitative data about the composition in the different layers has been obtained from EDX spectra, which were recorded by scanning areas of $150 \times 200 \text{ nm}^2$ during 30 seconds with an electron probe of about 500 pA. Because sets of suitable standards materials are missing for our study, standardless analysis without thickness correction was performed using the FEI TEM Imaging and Analysis (TIA) software in order to evaluate the film composition. The K-lines were used to quantify O, F, Mg and Ge elements. Beforehand, the integral intensities of the different lines were extracted with a great care (subtraction of the background with a multi-polynomial approach, fitting of the peaks with a non-linear least square method). We are aware that this approach can lead to inaccuracy in the composition measurement, especially for light elements like O or F (systematic error of around 10% to 20% are generally admitted [27]), but it allows providing at least a general compositional tendency. The validity of the measurement is also supported by similar analyses we did on other systems presenting well-controlled stoichiometry (SiO_2 and TiO_2 OAD layers obtained by evaporation, results not published). The results shown in Figure 5.c not only confirm that the Ge is highly oxidized (54 at.% of O), but they also indicate that the MgF_2 layer contains oxygen in a minor amount (3 at.%). It is worth to note here that the F/Mg atomic ratio obtained from EDX is very close to 2, as expected for the MgF_2 layer. In the Ge OAD layer, the EDX analyses performed in different regions (from the bottom to the top) indicate that the oxygen content is constant (within the uncertainties of the measurement). Across the nanocolumns of the OAD layer, the O/Ge atomic ratio is substantially smaller than that of GeO_2 compound expected from the IR measurements. However, such differences may be explained by heterogeneous distributions of the oxide in each column (surface oxidation) or by uncertainties of the EDX measurements.

3.4. Optical performances and perspective of optimization of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ bilayer

The analyses presented in the previous section clearly highlight the key role of the chemistry on the optical properties of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ system. To optimize the transmittance, the presence of water and GeO₂ must be avoided since their absorption peaks are centered in (or close to) the range of interest, 3.7-4.8 μm (refer to Figure 6.b). For this, a new bilayer was fabricated in which the bottom Ge OAD has been annealed at 200°C and was then, after opening the chamber to change the angle α to 0°, capped with MgF₂. These two layers were deposited on both sides of a thick silicon substrate (2 mm) for further optical characterizations and simulations. On **Figure 8.a**, the transmittance of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ bilayer is compared with the transmittance of the ideal AR design. The optimized Ge OAD/MgF₂ bilayer has a high maximum transmittance of 99.21% and very good average transmittance of 98.56% over 3.7-4.8 μm . This bilayer presents better performance than a typical commercial coating of 98% average transmission over 3.6-4.9 μm (representing a 0.56% transmittance average gain) [17] and similar efficiency compared with the best MWIR AR coating reported in the literature for Si and Ge optics [9]. However, simplicity of the design proposed in this paper enables a reduction of the manufacturing time and costs. Unfortunately, the experimental transmittance is still below the ideal design one.

To study other optimization paths of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ bilayer we have first simulated its optical characteristics (transmittance and ellipsometry). From the set of chemical information obtained by optical measurements and TEM, an optical model to simulate the behavior of the system was established. For the bottom layer, the model already described previously has been used: a BEMA, mixing Ge, GeO₂, water and void, using the optical properties of these compounds from literature. As pointed out from the STEM-EDX analysis, an intermixing layer is present between the Ge OAD and MgF₂ layer. This layer was also taken into account in the simulations using a BEMA mixing model. A graded concentration of MgF₂ mixed with

Ge-GeO₂ has been assumed for this intermixing layer simulating the concentration by decomposing this region into 10 sublayers with various concentration rates of MgF₂. Finally, a MgF₂ layer was added on top of this intermixing layer. On Figure 8(b,c) the optical simulation (ellipsometry and transmittance) of the experimental data using this model is presented. A schematic representation of this model is depicted on Figure 8.a.

As shown in Figure 8 (b,c), the very good agreement between the simulation and the experimental measurements gives credibility to the model used and consequently demonstrates the coherence between chemical and optical analyses. From this simulation, we were able to determine that the 406nm thick Ge OAD layer is composed of 12% of GeO₂, 44% of Ge, 40% of Air and 4% of water. The annealing process is thus able to reduce the amount of water present in the Ge OAD layer from a value of 11% to a value of 4% when sealed by a MgF₂ layer. The intermixing layer between the Ge OAD layer and the MgF₂ layer was found to be of a thickness of 39 nm with a MgF₂ volume fraction ranging from 55% at the bottom to 100% on top. Above it the MgF₂ layer was determined to be 672 nm thick.

Qualitatively, the TEM results are consistent with the optical model where the intermixing zone was determined to be 39 nm thick and with an MgF₂ concentration gradient. From a quantitative point of view, compositional information extracted from optical measurements and TEM are not directly comparable. In the case of ellipsometry, the simulations provide volume fractions of the different components present in the coating at a macroscopic scale (including porosity), while EDX gives elemental composition in individual nanocolumns. In order to compare these data, we can estimate roughly what should be the atomic composition of Ge and O from the volume fractions given by ellipsometry. For that purpose, voids contribution has been discarded and densities of amorphous Ge and GeO₂ taken from the literature have been used.[28,29] With these assumptions, a composition of 65 at. % of Ge and 35 at. % of O is estimated. This oxygen content in the nanocolumns estimated from

ellipsometry appears to be significantly lower than that obtained from EDX. These differences may be ascribed to the very local STEM-EDX technique.

In a context of optimization of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ bilayer, the sum of the simulated transmittance and absorption spectra (extracted from the optical model) are shown on Figure 8. These data demonstrate that it is possible to enhance the optical performances of the AR by reducing the absorption sources present in the Ge OAD layer, i.e. GeO₂ and H₂O. To support this assumption, we performed an *in-situ* spectrophotometric measurement while annealing under vacuum the Ge OAD/MgF₂ layer to a temperature of 200°C for 1h (blue spectrum of the Figure 8.c). The obtained spectrum is close to the summed simulated spectrum (absorption + transmittance). This result proves that an annealing allows suppressing efficiently the absorption caused by H₂O, enhancing the average transmittance value from 98.56% to 99.17%. Unfortunately, water is reabsorbed when exposing the annealed sample to atmospheric pressure, which suggests that the MgF₂ capping layer is probably not fully dense. The remaining difference between the design and the T+A spectrum is explained by the fact that the obtained refractive index of the Ge OAD layer (n=2.40) is not the optimal one (n=2.52).

Limiting the contamination and optimizing the refractive index of the Ge OAD layer will be the subject of further research. It will be made possible with the ongoing construction of a new home-made deposition chamber at the PPRIME Institute. This equipment, combining electron-beam and ion sputtering processes, will allow controlling finely and *in-situ* the deposition angle α . This approach will be considered in a close future to avoid oxidation phenomenon due to air exposure during the fabrication of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ system and to achieve a fine-tuning of the effective refractive indices.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we demonstrated that oblique angle deposition is a powerful approach to design and fabricate simple and high-performance antireflective surfaces for Si optics in the MWIR range. Taking into account fictive materials with effective refractive indices, we were able to design and simulate an AR coating with 99.97% transmittance over the 3.7-4.8 μm atmospheric window. This corresponds to a theoretical performance increase of about 2% compared to a standard AR system with dense materials. The optimization of the growth conditions, to obtain a bilayer made of a porous Ge OAD film with reduced effective refractive index and capped with a dense MgF_2 layer, allows achieving performances (98.56% average transmittance for 3.7-4.8 μm) similar to that of the best multilayered AR coatings reported in the literature, but with a much simpler structure suitable for large scale production. By combining IR ellipsometry, spectrophotometry and STEM-EDX analyses, it was pointed out that an important limiting factor for the transmittance is the presence of pollutants, more particularly GeO_2 and water, that lead to a degradation of the optical efficiency due to light absorption. *In-situ* optical measurements conducted during vacuum annealing showed that the performances of the AR system can be enhanced to 99.17% simply by evaporating water, opening new perspectives to achieve nearly perfect infrared transparency through the future improvements in the deposition process.

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Figure 1. Simulated transmittance spectra of an interferential (black) and an effective material bilayer (red) double sided AR coatings on silicon with their respective index profiles at $\lambda=4$ μm .

Figure 2. (a) SEM cross-section view (b) SEM tilted plane-view of a Ge OAD sample deposited at $\alpha=65^\circ$.

Figure 3. (a) Spectrophotometric and (b) ellipsometric measurements for a reflexion angle $\theta=65^\circ$ and 75° (black) of a $\alpha=65^\circ$ Ge OAD thin film and its simulations (red) obtained with a simple Ge/void BEMA.

Figure 4. Values of effective refractive index at $\lambda=4\mu\text{m}$ and changing porosity of Ge OAD thin films extracted from simulations with the simple BEMA optical model for various deposition angles.

Figure 5. Spectrophotometric measurement (black) of a $\alpha=65^\circ$ Ge OAD thin film and its simulation (red) with its BEMA model after considering water adsorption and oxidation.

Figure 6. (a) Ellipsometric measurements and simulations of Ge OAD film grown at a deposition angle of $\alpha=65^\circ$ for a reflexion angle $\theta=65^\circ$ and 75° . (b) Refractive index and extinction coefficient of the Ge OAD layer deposited at $\alpha=65^\circ$ obtained from ellipsometric (a), and spectrophotometric (Figure 5) simulations using the optical model described by Figure 5.

Figure 7. (a) Bright field TEM overview of the bilayer on Si. The insets correspond to the SAED patterns recorded in the different regions. (b) STEM-EDX analysis at the vicinity of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ interface. HAADF image and elemental maps obtained for Si, Ge, O, Mg and F atoms are presented. (c) EDX spectra and associated quantitative analyses of composition in the bottom and top layers.

Figure 8. Optical model of the Ge OAD/MgF₂ bilayer (a) simulating the ellipsometric (b) and spectrophotometric measurements (c).

Nanostructure Properties

Design

Infrared antireflective surface

Performance

Highlights:

- A simple antireflective design over 3.7-4.8 μm MWIR range is reported for Si substrate
- Ge-MgF₂ bilayer prepared by e-beam evaporation gives high performances ($T_{\text{av}}=98.56\%$)
- The refractive index of the Ge layer is tuned by Oblique Angle Deposition (OAD)
- Key insights about nanostructure, pollution and optical properties are provided
- New routes are proposed to keep on improving the performances